

Molecular Sorption on Ion-exchange Resins: Sorption of Coumarins

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The column sorption-desorption of coumarin with water and methanol as solvents and the comparative sorption of coumarin and twelve substituted coumarins in 10% methanol (by volume) on a strongly basic anion-exchange resin, Amberlite IRA-400, have been studied.

Sorption of weak non-electrolytes on ion-exchange resins has been investigated by several workers¹⁻²⁰; no study with coumarins is, however, available. So the column sorption-desorption of coumarin with water and methanol as solvents and the comparative sorption of coumarin and twelve substituted coumarins in 10% methanol (by volume) on a strongly basic anion-exchange resin, Amberlite IRA-400, are described herein.

EXPERIMENTAL

The resin used was Amberlite IRA-400 (Rohm and Haas Co.). This is a strongly basic anion-exchange resin, obtained by introducing strongly basic quaternary ammonium groups, as ionogenic groups, into a styrene divinylbenzene copolymer. The resin was air-dried and -40, +60 mesh fraction was used in this work.

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The resin was cycled thrice between sodium chloride and sodium hydroxide, finally regenerated with a large excess of sodium hydroxide, washed free of alkali, air-dried, and stored. The moisture content was estimated by drying samples (*ca.* 0.5g.) to a constant weight at 105°. For capacity estimation, weighed samples (*ca.* 0.5 g.) were placed in contact with 50 ml of standard HCl (*ca.* 0.1*N*) with intermittent shaking and the acid sorbed was estimated: Moisture content=21.15%; capacity per g. of air-dried and oven-dried resin = 2.035 m.e. and 2.58 m.e. respectively.

8-Hydroxy-, 7,8-dihydroxy-4-methyl-, and 7,8-dimethoxy-coumarins, obtained from Prof. S. M. Sethna's laboratory, were recrystallised and checked for melting points. Coumarin and rest of the substituted coumarins were from samples used in an earlier study²¹. HCl and NaOH of A.R. quality and distilled water and distilled methanol (B. D. H.) were used.

Coumarin and substituted coumarins were estimated in column effluent samples by UV absorption with a Beckman model DU spectrophotometer, using 10 mm quartz cells.

Run 1.—A resin column of the following column data was set up: capacity of the resin in the column = 92. m.e., bed volume = 123 ml, bed length = 53.5 cm, void-volume = 30 ml. An aqueous coumarin solution ($5.49 \times 10^{-4}M$) was passed downflow in the column at the rate of 10 ml/min. and 36 samples (each of 100 ml) were collected. The first sample included 30 ml of water from void-volume. The first sample and then even-numbered samples were estimated for coumarin. Let *a* and *b* denote for the sorption run the concentration (in g. moles/litre) of solute in the influent solution and effluent samples respectively; then $100(a-b)/a$ is denoted by *x*. The sorption curve is obtained by plotting *x* against the effluent sample number. The sorption curve obtained in this way is shown in Fig. 1, plot 1A.

After 36th sample, the column was drained, backwashed with distilled water, resin allowed to settle, and then distilled water was passed downflow at the rate of 10ml/min.; 36 samples (each of 100ml) were collected. The first and then the even numbered samples were estimated for coumarin. Let *b* denote the concentration of solute (in g. moles/litre) for the desorption run in the effluent samples. Then $100 b/a$ is denoted by *y* and the plot of *y* against effluent sample number provides the desorption curve. The plot 1B in Fig. 1 is the desorption curve obtained in this way. Fig. 1 indicates that, on the hydroxyl form of the resin used, the break-through for the sorption curve 1A is not sharp and the elution (1B) is slow.

Run 2.—Another resin column (capacity of the resin in the column=81.4 m.e.) was set up, a large excess of sodium chloride solution was passed, and then washed free of chloride ions with distilled water. The resin was then in chloride form and the column data were: bed volume = 112 ml, bed length=47 cm, void-volume=30ml. An aqueous solution of coumarin ($5.571 \times 10^{-4}M$) was passed downflow in the column at the rate of 10 ml/min. and 36 samples (each of 100 ml) were collected. The first sample included 30 ml of water from void-volume. The first and the even-numbered samples were estimated for coumarin. Fig. 2, plot 2A shows the sorption curve, obtained by the procedure noted above. The column was then drained, backwashed with distilled water, resin bed allowed to settle, and then distilled water passed downflow at the rate of 10 ml/min.; 36 samples, each of 100ml, were collected. The first and then even-numbered samples were estimated

for coumarin and the desorption curve 2B in Fig. 2 was obtained by the procedure detailed above.

Sample number.
FIG. 1

Sample number.
FIG. 2

Comparison of Fig. 1 and 2 indicates that the chloride form of resin used is more suitable for sorption-desorption of coumarin from aqueous solution than the hydroxyl form of the resin. From plot 2A (Fig. 2), the amount of coumarin sorbed per 100 m.e. of resin is calculated to be equal to 12.14×10^{-4} g. moles.

Run 3.—After run two, the same resin column was further washed with a large excess of distilled water, backwashed, and the resin allowed to settle. The aqueous coumarin

solution ($5.30 \times 10^{-4}M$; 3.6 litres) was passed downflow at the usual rate. The column was then drained, backwashed with methanol, and the resin bed allowed to settle. Then methanol was passed in the column downflow at the rate of 5ml/min. Ten samples (each of 100 ml) were collected and estimated for coumarin. The desorption curve obtained is shown in Fig. 3. Comparison of Fig. 3 and curve 2B in Fig 2 indicates that methanol is more suitable for desorption of coumarin for the chloride form of the resin used than water.

Sample number.
FIG. 3

Run 4.—After run three, the resin column was further washed with excess of methanol, backwashed with methanol, and the resin bed allowed to settle. A solution of coumarin in methanol ($55.0 \times 10^{-4}M$) was passed downflow in the column

at the rate of 5ml/min. The samples (100 ml each) were collected and estimated for

coumarin. The first sample included 30 ml of solvent from void-volume. The values of x for first three effluent samples were: 75.5, 4.2, and 0.0. The coumarin sorbed per 100 m.e. of resin is calculated to be equal to 3.85×10^{-4} g. moles. A comparison with sorption run in run 2 indicates that though the ratio of coumarin concentrations in influent solution is 9.87, the ratio of the amounts of coumarin sorbed per 100 m.e. of resin is only 0.317. This supports that methanol is less suitable for sorption and more suitable for desorption of coumarin on the chloride form of the resin.

Run 5.—Another column of the resin (capacity of the resin in the column = 6.1 m.e.) was set up and the resin converted to chloride form. Excess of 10% methanol (by volume) was then passed in the column. The column data were: bed volume = 7.3 ml; bed length = 15.2 cm. A solution of coumarin in 10% methanol ($5.55 \times 10^{-4} M$) was passed in the column downflow at the rate of 10 ml/min. and samples (100 ml each) were collected. Curve 5 in Fig. 4 shows the sorption curve obtained by plotting x against sample number. The column was then washed with excess of each of methanol, methanolic hydrochloric acid, distilled water, aqueous sodium hydroxide, distilled water, aqueous sodium chloride, distilled water, and 10% methanol. The column was then backwashed with 10% methanol and the resin bed allowed to settle.

FIG. 4

Run 6—17.—Runs were repeated, using the procedure set for run 5, with solutions ($5.55 \times 10^{-4} M$) in 10% methanol for each of the following: 7,8-diMeO-C,* 6,7-diMeO-C, 8-MeO-C, 3-Me-C, 7-Me-C, 8-OH-C, 6-OH-4Me-C, 7-OH-C, 7-OH-4-Me-C, 5-OH-4-Me-C, 6,7-diOH-4-Me-C, and 7, 8-diOH-4-Me-C. The sorption curves (6 to 17) are shown in Fig. 4.

* O denotes coumarin.

The family of 13 sorption curves (5 to 17) in Fig. 4 indicates that coumarin and methoxy-, methyl-, and hydroxy-coumarins are sorbed on the chloride form of strongly basic anion-exchange resin used in 10% methanol. The sorption increases in the order: coumarin < methoxycoumarins < methylcoumarins < hydroxycoumarins. For methoxycoumarins, the sorption study indicates that sorption increases in the order: dimethoxy < monomethoxy and 8-methoxy < 6-methoxy. On the other hand, the sorption for hydroxycoumarins increases in the order: monohydroxy < dihydroxy and 6-hydroxy < 8-hydroxy < 7-hydroxy < 5-hydroxy.

In an earlier study²¹, it was observed that from the UV absorption maxima, hydroxy and methoxy substitution, when the substitution was in 5,6,7, or 8 position in the benzene ring of coumarin, could not be distinguished; also, the same was true for 5- and 8-hydroxycoumarins. Fig. 4 indicates that such cases could be distinguished from their sorption curves.

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